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Abstract. In the article, the causes of kidney failure in the human body shown. In diseases accompanied by damage to renal vessels kidney damage: scleroderma, thrombocytopenic purpura, etc., kidney under diseases, a wide group of pathological changes produced by the body dysfunction and then complete failure.

Key words: Kidney diseases, perennial kidney failure; postrenal kidney deficiency; renal failure.

The human body receives almost all necessary substances through food and water. The composition of food products and their properties for health, physical development, ability to work, emotional state and, in general, life expectancy and directly affects the quality. It was able to affect the human body so much it is difficult to find another factor. Analysis of kidney failure based on the following it is appropriate to do.

Kidney diseases are an obstacle to the normal functioning of these organs of the urinary system includes various pathologies. Each of the kidney diseases characteristics, different clinical manifestations. In fact, many kidney diseases are asymptomatic, i.e without symptoms, and patients about existing problems with their health they don't know

Prerenal. This is due to impaired renal blood flow. Sufficient amount for kidney no blood. As a result, the process of urine formation is disturbed, the kidney tissue is pathological changes will occur. It occurs in about half of patients (55%).

Conditions in which the heart cannot perform its tasks and pumps less blood:

- arrhythmia, heart failure, heavy bleeding, thromboembolism of the pulmonary artery.
- Sudden drop in blood pressure: shock (sepsis) in gross infections, severe allergic reactions, overdosage of some drugs.

Dehydration: severe vomiting, diarrhea, burns, overdose of diuretics use

Cirrhosis and other liver diseases: in which the reflow of venous blood is disturbed, tumors develop, blood supply to the cardiovascular system and kidneys is disrupted.

Renal. It is related to the pathology of kidney tissue. Kidney with blood is sufficiently supplied, but cannot produce urine. It occurs in 40% of patients. Poisonings: poisonous substances in everyday life and industry, snakes, insects stings, heavy metals, overdoses of some drugs. Entering the bloodstream, it is poisonous substances reach the kidneys and disrupt their work.

Massive breakdown of erythrocytes and hemoglobin: in incompatible blood transfusions, in malaria. In this case, kidney tissues are damaged.

In autoimmune diseases, for example, in myeloma, the kidney with antibodies damage In some diseases, the kidneys are damaged by metabolic products, for example, with uric acid salts in gout.

Inflammatory process in the kidneys: glomerulonephritis, with kidney syndrome hemorrhagic fever, etc.

Damage to the kidneys in diseases with damage to the renal vessels reach:

- scleroderma, thrombocytopenic purpura, etc.

• Injury of a single kidney (if the second one does not work for some reason). Postrenal. Urine is produced in the kidney, but due to an obstruction in the ureter can't get out. If the obstruction is only in the urinary tract, it is a damaged kidney a healthy kidney takes over its function - kidney failure does not occur. This the condition occurs in 5% of patients.

- Tumors of the prostate, bladder, other organs in the small pelvis.
- Injury to the urinary tract during surgery or accidental ligation.
- Urinary tract obstruction: possible causes are thrombosis, pus, stone, congenital development defects. Urinary disorders, chronic due to taking certain drugs causes kidney failure: Congenital and hereditary kidney diseases.

- Kidney damage in chronic diseases: gout, diabetes, urinary stones disease, obesity, metabolic syndrome, liver cirrhosis, systemic lupus erythematosus, scleroderma and others.

- Urine in which gradual obstruction of the urinary tract occurs various diseases of the system: urolithiasis, tumor, etc.

- Kidney diseases: chronic glomerulonephritis, chronic pyelonephritis.

- Incorrect use of drugs, overdose.

- Chronic poisoning with various toxic substances. Symptoms of acute kidney failure depend on its stage:

- Acute kidney failure can damage the kidneys, which is blood loss, toxins or can occur as a result of physical damage to the kidneys. Acute kidney deficiency appears and resolves rapidly, and confusion disappears causes general symptoms. This is a serious condition, but it can be treated, and With proper treatment, most people survive an episode of kidney failure long-term can live without consequences.

The kidney controls the amount of fluid, electrolytes and waste in the body and sends excess materials to be lost in the urine. Acute kidney Symptoms of deficiency of these substances accumulate in the body, because the kidneys need it does not work when For optimal functioning of the whole body, normal fluid and electrolyte levels are required. Waste materials are the body's cells and it is toxic to the tissues in large quantities, which causes a wide range of symptoms. Sharp symptoms of kidney failure develop rapidly over several hours or days, the main reasons for this are:

Blood pressure on the kidneys, drugs, general health, nutrition and man many factors affect it, such as the amount of drinking water. Acute kidney failure there are different ways this can happen. Anything that damages the kidneys quickly reduces the amount of work they can do. Acute kidney failure it can be temporary or it can be a sign of bigger problems. There are three main categories of causes of acute kidney failure.

Kidney the term describes the kidneys, and the names of these categories are prerenal, intrinsic, and postrenal.

Prerenal: This is the kidney that begins before the blood reaches the kidneys describes the reasons for its deficiency. For example, low blood pressure, if the heart It happens when your body isn't working effectively or you're severely dehydrated.

In this case, the kidneys themselves are not the main problem, but they are low blood is affected by the supply, which filters the blood of the kidneys makes it difficult. Severe infection can lead to septic shock, in which the kidneys can cause damage, because blood pressure effectively work the kidneys falls to an impossibly low level.

Internal: the causes of kidney failure caused by damage to the kidneys themselves describes. Toxins, including chemicals, illegal drugs and even some drugs can pass through the kidneys and damage them.

Medicines that can cause acute kidney failure examples include contrast materials for vision tests. All these drugs are them does not cause acute renal failure in any person or no one ever uses them. But they are a kidney for some people may cause a deficiency and predict that you will have this reaction can be difficult. Sometimes acute kidney which can lead to deficiency blood tests that measure kidney function before taking medication may be necessary.

Other that can lead to internal kidney failure in cases of lack of oxygen in the blood, kidney infection, inflammation in the kidneys and there are kidney diseases. A very large kidney stone can also cause internal damage to the kidney possible

Summary: Kidneys are the most important organ for the human body. Body through the kidneys it is cleaned of unnecessary substances. These are the real working bodies that carry out permanent work. Any kidney damage means that the body cannot get rid of harmful substances and gradually leads to non-initiation of self-determination. Therefore, the kidney to identify problems in time and take all measures to treat them very important.

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